

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *LEUCONOSTOC MESENTEROIDES* ISOLATED FROM RAW GOAT MILK

 Kihal Mebrouk

Ahmed Ben Bella University, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology, Oran, Algeria

*Corresponding Author:
E-mail: nabila10hansal@outlook.com

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ABSTRACT. *Leuconostoc* are widespread in the natural environment and play an important role in several fermentations due to their physiological characteristics. With the aim of studying the biological potential of these bacteria four samples of goat raw milk were collected from north-western Algeria and used as sources of isolation of *Leuconostoc*. A total of 12 isolates of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* were obtained by sequential screening for morphological, chemically and MALDI-TOF identification tests. All isolates were observed to behave antagonistically with all indicator strains, with differences in the size of the inhibition zone by the stain diffusion method. Contrariwise to the results of the diffusion method, only seven strains of these isolates were able to inhibit Gram-positive strains with variable resistance according to each strain after heat resistance tests (60°C to 120°C) and acidity (pH 2 to 9) with complete disappearance of this inhibitory activity when their supernatant was treated with pepsin and α -chymotrypsin. The strain W9 was selected as the most efficient to study its capacity of bio-preservation food by the follow-up of the kinetics of pH, the production of lactic acid and the growth in pure culture and mixed with strains of spoilages and/or pathogens. The results obtained showed that these isolates have important antagonistic and conservative potential. It could be concluded that they could be effective candidates for a local application of bio-conservation.

Keywords: Antagonistic, bio-preservation, fermentations, *leuconostoc*, MALDI-TOF.

INTRODUCTION

The use of microorganisms such as Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) with antagonistic properties and/or their antimicrobial metabolites that can increase the shelf life of foodstuffs, the LAB fermentation process is known as a traditional bio-preservation process [1, 2, 3, 4]. LAB have been used to prolong storage, enhance nutritive and therapeutic values and promote changes in flavor, texture and tastes [2] due to the production of organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, diacetyl and bacteriocins with antagonistic microbiological properties to suppress the growth of undesirable microbiota [4]. LAB has been applied to dairy products, vegetables, meat, and fish [1].

The genus *Leuconostoc* is one of the main bacterial genus of LAB used in fermented foods found from the initial to the middle stage of fermentation [5]. As a heterofermentative bacterium, *Leuconostoc* transforms glucose molecules into carbon dioxide ethanol and lactate. In addition, low molecular weight organic compounds produced by *Leuconostoc* provide aroma and flavor to the fermented products [6].

Leuconostoc and other LAB are generally recognized as safe (GRAS) and have been widely used all around the world to improve the preservation, sensorial characteristics and nutritional value of various products, including milk, meat and vegetables. *Leuconostoc* spp. is found in

many natural ecological niches such as green vegetation and roots from where they are easily able to propagate into various environments such as vegetables, silage [7] and fermented food products. Also, *Leuconostoc* spp. has been isolated from feces and breast milk in several research studies [8].

Furthermore, *Leuconostoc* spp. play an important economic roles in the fermentation of foodstuffs such as vegetables (sauerkraut, pickles, etc.); generation of carbon dioxide gas in cheeses (especially blue-veined cheeses) providing pores; production of flavoring compounds in many dairy products; in situ production of dextran in saccharose-containing products; high-value polymers for industrial or clinical use; value polymers for industrial or clinical use; as well as potential roles in functional foods [6].

Biopreservation is defined as the use of antagonistic microbes and their metabolites to inhibit undesired microbes to increase safety and shelf-life [9]. The ability of *Leuconostoc* spp. isolated from raw goat milk to promote safety or quality is linked to excreted organic acids and subsequent pH reduction, and many other antimicrobial compounds such as CO₂, diacetyl and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) [10]. In addition, the ability to produce bacteriocins with inhibitory effects on Gram positive bacteria, is well-described for *Leuconostocs* spp. isolated from raw goat's milk against spoilage and pathogenic bacteria [11].

Additionally, *Leuconostoc* strains have potential as protective cultures for vacuum packed meat products, and the bacteriocins of *Leuconostoc* can be used as protective agents in combination with another starter culture in fermented meat [12].

This study aims to calibrate and detect strains of *Leuconostoc* spp. which have a remarkable antagonistic potential against some strains of spoilages and/or pathogens, isolated from the local raw goat milk, intended to be used as a bio-preservative agent for future food applications after proteomic identification by the use of MALDI-TOF stands for Matrix Associated Laser Desorption-Ionization - Time of Flight and consists of a system in which biological material (a colony or a blood culture concentrate) is performed to identify stains. The sample strains of this study were identified at CRAPC (Center scientific and technical research in physico-chemical analysis) located in Tipaza, Algeria, using MALDI-TOF Biotyper 4.0 (Bruker Daltonic, Germany).

This method analyzes the protein composition of a microbial cell. Comparative studies have shown that MALDI-TOF MS is a comparatively effective identification technique. This statement is based on the reproducibility, speed and sensitivity of the analysis [13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Milk sample collection

Four raw goat milk samples were collected directly from dairy farms located in Saida (north-western Algeria). For the sample collection, the udder of a goat was washed twice with sterilized water and disinfected with 70% ethanol. Furthermore, a volume of 100 ml of milk from each goat was collected aseptically in sterile bottles. The samples were transported immediately under refrigeration (4°C) to the microbiology laboratory of the Department of Microbiology, University of Oran1 Ahmed Ben Bella, Algeria, for further analysis.

Isolation of Leuconostoc spp.

The *Leuconostoc* spp. strains were isolated from milk, by the dilution of a volume of 10 ml of each milk samples in 90 ml saline solution and the suitable serial dilutions were plated on the MRS Agar (Mann Rogosa Sharpe) supplemented with 30 µg/ml Vancomycine (MRSV) [14] and on Agar MSE. Then, inoculated plates were incubated at 30°C for 48 hours. The typical colonies were isolated and purified by successive subcultures between agar and MRSV medium broth, until colonies of the same size, same shape, and same color were obtained, providing

information on the purity of the strains. The short-time conservation of the pure isolates was achieved on a solid culture medium. The obtained culture was maintained at 4°C and renewed every month.

Physiological and biochemical characterization

The isolates were characterized on the basis of physiological and biochemical tests, such as cellular form, catalase, oxidase tests and gas production from glucose according to the described method by Thomas [15]. Additionally, hydrolysis of arginine and citric acid degradation on Kempler and McKay solid medium, fermentation of carbohydrates, tolerance to NaCl concentration (3% and 6.5%), growth at different pH (4.5, 6.5 and 9), growth at different temperatures (4°C, 15°C, 30°C, 37°C, and 45°C) and heat resistance at 60°C/30 min and 55 C/15 min. Acetoin production was revealed by a red ring after the addition of the reagents VP1 and VP2 in the KMK broth fermented with the lactic isolates, were carried out [16]. Carbohydrate fermentation was performed on MRS supplemented with bromocresol purple as a pH indicator using the following sugars to differentiate between the subspecies of *Leuconostoc* spp. arabinose, esculine, fructose, galactose, glucose, lactose, maltose, mannitol, rhamnose, sorbitol, sucrose and xylose. The incubation of these tests was performed at 30°C for 48h.

Identification using MALDI-TOF

The identification process with MALDI-TOF MS was carried out in several steps. Colonies of the selected isolates were plated in the wellbore of the microplate on which a matrix (α -hydroxamic acid sinamic) was added. The mixture was dried for 5min. After, the formic acid was added for the extraction of the proteins from the bacterium analyzed. Then, the samples were dried again.

The samples were irradiated with a laser that vaporizes the samples with the ionization of several molecules, which are sucked into a vacuum tube that leads to a detector. The flight time varies depending on the molecule. Finally, it is transferred to a graph with several peaks and each bacterial species has a specific graph or spectrum called PMF (Peptide Mass Fingerprint) [17, 18].

The system scans for microbial proteins that primarily fall within the range of 4000 to 20,000 Daltons (60% to 70% of the dry cell weight of bacteria). The spectrum instantly matches the reference library to give the genera and species of the strains identified by comparison to the spectra that are displayed on the software, while the spectrum of unidentified strains represents the absence of comparison spectra in the database [19].

Nature investigation of the antimicrobial substance

Direct method (by spot) and indirect method (diffusion method)

Preliminary screening for the antagonistic activity of *Leuconostoc* isolates was carried out on a solid media by the direct method (by spot) described by Fleming *et al.* [20]. The activity was investigated on the following indicator bacteria: *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090), *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC19119), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC25923), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Salmonella montevideo* (ATCC 3581) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC27853) [21, 22].

The indirect method (diffusion method) using a cell-free supernatant (CFS) with inhibition of the effect of lactic acid was obtained according to the protocol described by [11]. Inhibition was considered as positive result when the width of the inhibition halos was sharp ≥ 0.5 cm.

Characterization of the inhibitory substance

Search lysogenic phages

A piece of agar in the zone of inhibition was cut with a Pasteur pipette. This fragment was suspended in 1 ml of sterile medium containing 50 µl of chloroform. After stirring, it was allowed to settle for 5min, then 300 µl of this mixture was taken and added to 7 ml of fine agar containing the indicator strain of soft agar containing the indicator strain. The mixture was poured aseptically into a Petri dish and incubated for 48 h at 28°C. The presence of lysis plaque indicated the presence of phage [23].

Effect of temperature on the extracted inhibitory substance

To explore the effect of temperature on the extracted inhibitory substance, a volume of 5 ml of supernatant was introduced in different test tubes and heated at 60°C/30 min, 80°C/15 min, 100°C/15 min and at 120°C for 10 min under pressure [24]. The heat-treated inhibitory substance samples were employed for antimicrobial activity assay as described above [11].

Effect of pH on the extracted inhibitory substance

To investigate the effect of pH value on the extracted inhibitory substance, a volume of 5 ml of supernatant was introduced in different test tubes to adjust each supernatant to a pH value (2, 4 and 9) using 1 mol / l NaOH or 1 mol / l HCl solution, incubated at 37 ° C. for 2 h [24].

Effect of proteolytic enzyme on the extracted inhibitory substance

The effect of the proteolytic enzyme activity on the extracted inhibitory substance was investigated by the incubation of bacterial supernatant in the presence of one of the enzymes (pepsin and α-chymotrypsin) at a final concentration of 1 mg/ml and incubated at 37°C for 1h [24].

Acidity and growth kinetics in pure and mixed cultures

The next phase consisted in studying the growth kinetics of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* (W9) in pure cultures and cultures mixed with six strains indicative of degradation and/or pathogenic strains: "Gram-positive strains: *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090) and *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119); *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923) and Gram-negative strains: *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922); *Salmonella Montevideo* (ATCC 3581) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853)".

Then, they were incubated separately (each in its solid selective medium). A colony of each of them was inoculated into their selective liquid medium and incubated at 30°C for 18 h. After, 100 µl of each 18 h culture was inoculated into 10 ml of skim milk containing 0.3% yeast extract and incubated at 18°C for 18 h [20]. To this end, two sets of eight tubes of 10 ml each for each strain studied were obtained. The first was used to study the kinetics of growth and the second, to study the kinetics of acidification (acidity and pH) in pure culture.

The same steps were followed for the experience in mixed culture except, where 50 µl of W9 pre-culture was mixed in 10 ml of sterile skim milk with 50 µl of one of the indicator bacteria. [25]. Every three hours, the samples were aseptically withdrawn from tubes to determine the pH, tritable acidity and the growth rate. These experiments were performed in triplicate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phenotypical identification of isolates

The physiological characteristics of Twelve isolates from raw goat milk were identified based on the physiological and biochemical characteristics specific to the genus *Leuconostoc* such as ovoid shape, Gram positivity, catalase negativity, oxidase negativity, lack of arginine hydrolysis and production of gas from glucose) [26]. the results are presented in (Table 1).

Furthermore, the isolates were able to grow at 15 and 37°C but not at 4 and 45°C, which confirms that it was mesophilic bacteria, not able to resist at 63.5°C for 30 min, but at 55°C for 15 min. These results are in good agreement to those found by Ogier *et al.* [27].

In addition, the isolates were able to stand a concentration of 3% of NaCl, but they did not grow at 6.5% NaCl and were able to grow at pH 6.5 and not at pH 4.8. These results are similar to those reported by Hui *et al.* [26], whose strains of *Leuconostoc* do not have the capacity to resist a concentration of 6.5% of NaCl nor a pH of 4.8.

All the strains were able to produce dextran, use citrate, thanks to the presence of the citratase enzyme which is an important criterion for the selection of species of technological interest (Table 2). This observation has already been reported by Bellengier *et al.* [28].

All strains were unable to produce acetoin from glucose, which corresponds to the characteristics of the two subspecies *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* subsp. *Mesenteroides* and *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* subsp. *dextranicum* [14]. According to the fermentation, the results showed that ten out of Twelve isolates belong to the species *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* subsp. *mesenteroides* (LN29P, LN31, LN39, LN44, LN46, LV5, LV3, LY36, W9 and W10) (Table 3). Whereas arabinose is the key of distinction between the subspecies of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*, according to Mathot *et al.* [14].

Table 1: The main phenotypic and physiological characteristics of the isolated bacteria

The strains	Test					
	Cell form	Gram	Catalase	Oxidase	ADH	Fermentation type
LN29P	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
LN31	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
LN39	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
LN44	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
LN46	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
Lv5	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
Lv3	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
LY36	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
W9	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
W10	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
E3	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative
L19	Ovoid shape	+	-	-	-	Heterofermentative

-: Negative results

+: Positive results

Table 2: Physiological and biochemical characterization of the 12 strains tested

The strains	Test											
	Different T °				Thermal resistance		NaCl tolerance		Different pH			Citrate
	4°	15°	37°	45°	63.5° 30 min	55° 15min	3%	6.5%	4.5	6.5	9	
LN29P	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
LN31	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
LN39	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
LN44	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
LN46	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
Lv5	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
Lv3	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
LY36	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
W9	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
W10	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
E3	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
L19	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+

-: Negative results, +: Positive results

All strains were unable to produce acetoin from glucose, which corresponds to the characteristics of the two subspecies *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* subsp. *Mesenteroides* and *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* subsp. *dextranicum* [14]. According to the fermentation, the results showed that ten out of Twelve isolates belong to the species *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* subsp. *mesenteroides* (LN29P, LN31, LN39, LN44, LN46, LV5, LV3, LY36, W9 and W10) (Table 3). Whereas arabinose is the key of distinction between the subspecies of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*, according to Mathot *et al.* [14].

Table 3: Fermentation profile of *Leuconostoc* strains isolated from raw goat's milk

Fermentation profile	<i>Leuconostoc</i> isolates	
	The ten Strains of <i>Leuconostoc</i> named by: LN29P, LN31, LN39, LN44, LN46, LV5, LV3, LY36, W9 and W10	The two Strains of <i>Leuconostoc</i> named by: E3 and L19
Arabinose	+	-
Esculine	±	-
Fructose	+	+
Galctose	+	+
Gluctose	+	+
Lactose	+	+
Maltose	+	+
Mannitol	-	-
Rhamnose	-	-
Sorbitol	-	-
Suctose	+	+
Xylose	±	±

-: Negative results, +: Positive results, ±: Intermediate results

Identification using MALDI-TOF

The objective of microbial identification is to differentiate one microbial isolate from another and then to place that isolate into a family and a species or even as a particular. The MALDI-TOF technique is based on the principle that time is related to mass and that this can be measured under high vacuum conditions. The higher the mass, the lower its velocity and the longer it takes before the ion strikes the detector. Therefore, this leads to different microorganisms forming different patterns or 'spectra.' The resultant protein spectra can be compared to a database and a match made. The spectrum of an identifier microorganism obtained with the MALDI BIOTYPER is then compared with the recorded mass spectra. The software used during this experimentation is called MALDI BIOTYPER [29].

A score is calculated by multiplying three factors (each factor can reach a maximum of 1), namely the correspondences of the unknown spectrum against the main spectrum (MSP), the correspondences of the MSP against the unknown spectrum and the similarity of the intensity profile of the corresponding peaks. The logarithm of these calculated scores (multiplied by 1000) gives the $\log(\text{score})$, maximum 3 ($\log(1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 1000) = 3$) [30].

All $\log(\text{score})$ are ranked from the highest to the lowest. The match with the highest $\log(\text{score})$ results in a species-level identification if a threshold is exceeded $\log(\text{score}) \geq 1.9$ identification indicator species, $\log(\text{score})$ of 1.7-1.9 indicated gender identification, and $\log(\text{score}) < 1.7$ indicated no identification [31].

The analysis performed with MALDI-TOF/MS confirmed that all the strains belonged to the genus *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* with a score that exceeds 1.7 (Table 4) of which four strains were identified at the species level by a value exceeding 2 of the score (Fig.1).

Table 4: Identification of the isolated strains by the MALDI-TOF/MS method with the “log score value” of similarities

Strains	Identification by MALDI-TOF	Log score value
LN29P	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.86
LN31	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	2.01
LN39	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.89
LN44	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.92
LN46	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.81
Lv5	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.79
E3	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1,79
LY36	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	2,11
W9	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	2,16
W10	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	2,01
L19	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.85
LV3	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	1.78

Fig.1. Spectra for different strains of *Leuconostoc* spp (source: raw goat milk)

A) Spectra of the LN31 strain, B) Spectra of the LN46 strain, C) Spectra of the W9 strain, D) Spectra of the W10 strain

Antimicrobial activity of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*

Direct method (by spot)

Twelve strains exhibited inhibitory activity against all tested indicator strains *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090) and *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Salmonella Montevideo* (ATCC 3581) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853).

Figure 2 shows the different zones of inhibition. This antimicrobial activity is described by the bio-preservative role of LAB, including *Leuconostoc*. It is linked to the production of compounds that inhibit the growth of pathogenic and spoilage competitors by the production of active molecules due to metabolism, in particular, hydrogen peroxide, organic acids like lactic acid, acetic acid, diacetyl (lethal for Gram-negative bacteria, yeasts, and molds; bacteriostatic for Gram-positive bacteria), and ethanol that affect the membrane and the cell integrity at the level of membrane potential, lipids and transport systems [32].

Fig.2. Inhibition of pathogens and/or alteration by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* using a direct method

- A) Inhibition of *L. innocua* (ATCC 33090) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
- B) Inhibition of *L. ivanovii* (ATCC 19119) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
- C) Inhibition of *Stap.s aureus* (ATCC 25923) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
- D) Inhibition of *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
- E) Inhibition of *Sal. montevideo* (ATCC 3581) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
- F) Inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*

Indirect method (diffusion method)

The twelve isolates were reconsidered for their antagonistic activity against the six previous indicator strains using a diffusion method. Seven isolates manifested an excellent antagonistic activity against the tested Gram-positive after acid was removed. Furthermore, the isolates did not show any antagonistic activity against the investigated Gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli*, *Sal. montevideo* and *P. aeruginosa*.

These results suggest that the main antimicrobial effect of these strains depends on the acid knowing that the acidifying function is the most sought after of lactic acid bacteria which has the effect of a significant production of lactic acid leading to a lasting acidification of the medium in order to inhibit the growth of harmful microorganisms [33] and the bacteriostatic effect of hydrogen peroxide [34]. All isolates manifested antagonistic activity with diameter of inhibition zone greater than 8 mm were used for further studies such as characterization of the inhibitory substance (Fig.3), (Table5).

Fig. 3. Inhibition of pathogens and/or alteration by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* using a diffusion method

- A) Inhibition of *L. innocua* (ATCC 33090) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
 B) Inhibition of *L. ivanovii* (ATCC 19119) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*
 C) Inhibition of *Stap. aureus* (ATCC 25923) by *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*

Characterization of the inhibitory substance

Search lysogenic phages

Many bacteria produce phages spontaneously. These phages may be detected by testing culture filtrates on indicator bacteria because most of the phages are specific to their host genus [35]. The results of this study show no inhibition due to lysogeny for all strains, therefore, bacterial antagonism is due to another inhibitory source such as bacteriocins. Wood and Holzapfel [36] confirmed that, until now, *Leuconostoc* phage attacks have never been described in the dairy field. In addition, many *Leuconostoc* spp. produce exopolysaccharides that could protect the bacteria against phage adsorption.

Effect of temperature

The obtained results showed that the antagonistic activity of the produced inhibitory substance by the seven strains (LN39, W9, W10, LV5, LN29p, E3, and LN46) of *Leuconostoc* selected against Gram-positive indicator bacteria, was decreased after treatment (60°C/30 min, 80°C/15 min, 100°C/15 min), until complete disappearance at 120°C/10min for most strains tested (Fig.4) (Table 5).

These results point to the explanation given by Pranckute *et al.* [37]. The authors reported that the molecular weight of antimicrobial peptides, which are secondary protein structures (α -helix, β -folding, β -rotation angle, and random crimp), is between 3 and 10 kDa as this low molecular weight and secondary structure can lead to the high-temperature resistance of most antimicrobial peptides.

Fig.4. Effect of different degrees of temperature (60,80, 100 and 120°C) on antimicrobial activity

- a) the antimicrobial activity of W9 strain against *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090),
- b) the antimicrobial activity of E3 strain against *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119)

Effect of pH and proteolytic enzyme

The obtained results showed a considerable reduction of the antagonistic activity of the produced inhibitory substance by *Leuconostoc* strains at pH 2. Moreover, the optimum pH value for the antagonistic activity was between 4 and 9 (Fig.5), (Table5). Similar results were reported by Blajman *et al.* [34] for the antibacterial substance produced by *Leuconostoc* strains (Y44 and Y46) isolated from raw dromedary milk.

Fig. 5. Effect of trypsin, α -chymotrypsin and different pH values (2, 4, 7 and 9) on the antimicrobial activity against *Listeria sp.*

- a) the antimicrobial activity of W9 strain against *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090)
- b) the antimicrobial activity of E3 strain against *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119)

The effects of various proteases on the inhibitory agent showed a considerable loss of antagonistic activity against pathogenic bacteria after treatment with pepsin and α -chymotrypsin, indicating that the active compounds of these substances have protein character; this is a general characteristic of bacteriocin. Therefore, these characteristics allow the use of these antimicrobial compounds in food products because they are stable to the conditions applied during the manufacturing and processing process [34].

Table 5: Inhibitory activity of neutralized supernatants of *Leuconostoc* strains isolated from goat raw milk under the effect of different pH values and of different Temperature.

	pH effect							Temperature effect			
	7	2	4	9	9	60°C/30min	80°C/15min	100°C/15min	120°C/10min		
LN39+Stap.	9.00±0.17	-	5.15±0.18	4.00±0.20	4.00±0.20	7.45±0.27	6.15±0.12	4.00±0.15	2.00±0.29		
LN39+LC.	10.50±0.16	-	4.21±0.16	5.60±0.16	5.60±0.16	6.39±0.13	5.21±0.12	2.03±0.14	-		
LN39+LV.	10.45±0.15	-	5.27±0.15	5.03±0.17	5.03±0.17	7.21±0.13	5.03±0.12	3.00±0.15	-		
W9+Stap.	12.50±0.14	-	7.45±0.13	5.57±0.14	5.57±0.14	7.24±0.19	6.21±0.12	4.51±0.12	2.50±0.12		
W9+LC.	16.51±0.13	-	8.54±0.12	9.45±0.13	9.45±0.13	8.42±0.12	6.39±0.11	4.51±0.11	2.14±0.12		
W9+LV.	15.00±0.13	-	6.60±0.13	8.39±0.12	8.39±0.12	7.57±0.12	6.36±0.12	3.50±0.12	2.20±0.25		
W10+Stap.	11.30±0.14	-	5.39±0.15	7.54±0.14	7.54±0.14	7.00±0.16	6.00±0.14	3.00±0.18	-		
W10+LC.	15.00±0.14	-	6.21±0.15	7.48±0.16	7.48±0.16	8.00±0.18	7.06±0.16	4.51±0.21	2.13±0.18		
W10+LV.	15.00±0.14	-	7.42±0.14	8.36±0.15	8.36±0.15	8.39±0.15	6.12±0.14	3.30±0.16	2.08±0.27		
Lv5+Stap.	12.33±0.16	-	4.18±0.16	6.03±0.13	6.03±0.13	7.06±0.10	5.00±0.26	3.00±0.28	-		
Lv5+LC.	13.27±0.18	-	5.48±0.20	6.27±0.20	6.27±0.20	6.12±0.27	4.54±0.24	3.00±0.28	-		
Lv5+LV.	14.09±0.19	-	9.15±0.20	7.36±0.23	7.36±0.23	8.09±0.26	5.00±0.21	3.51±0.21	2.00±0.22		
LN29P+Stap.	8.24±0.17	-	4.45±0.15	5.39±0.18	5.39±0.18	6.24±0.12	4.00±0.15	2.03±0.14	-		
LN29P+LC.	10.30±0.14	-	3.12±0.12	5.51±0.12	5.51±0.12	7.39±0.07	5.03±0.15	2.00±0.17	-		
LN29P+LV.	11.24±0.13	-	5.00±0.13	5.42±0.14	5.42±0.14	7.42±0.16	5.00±0.14	3.30±0.18	-		
E3+Stap.	9.21±0.13	-	4.09±0.13	5.09±0.13	5.09±0.13	6.27±0.12	4.00±0.17	2.50±0.12	-		
E3+LC.	11.18±0.13	-	6.54±0.13	7.39±0.12	7.39±0.12	7.00±0.12	4.00±0.12	2.00±0.28	-		
E3+LV.	10.15±0.13	-	5.06±0.14	4.12±0.15	4.12±0.15	6.00±0.19	3.00±0.23	2.00±0.17	-		
LN46+Stap.	12.90±0.12	-	4.57±0.12	5.03±0.13	5.03±0.13	5.54±0.12	4.45±0.25	3.50±0.25	2.00±0.50		
LN46+LC.	14.16±0.12	-	6.03±0.12	6.00±0.12	6.00±0.12	6.36±0.12	5.21±0.25	3.14±0.25	-		
LN46+LV.	15.33±0.12	-	8.60±0.12	9.00±0.12	9.00±0.12	7.21±0.12	5.00±0.25	3.20±0.50	-		

-: Absence of inhibition.

Stap.: *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923)**LC.:** *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090)**LV.:** *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119)

Kinetic monitoring of pH, acidity and kinetic growth

The control of the pH of the *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* W9 strain in pure and mixed culture indicated that indicator strains of alterations and/or pathogens were all less acidifying in pure culture in a dairy medium. This result was observed by a drop in pH from neutral at 0 h incubation to (5.3 ± 0.13 for *L. innocua*, 5.6 ± 0.13 for *L. ivanovii*, 5.5 ± 0.35 for *Stap. aureus*, 5.4 ± 0.06 for *E. coli*, 5.2 ± 0.11 for *Sal. montevideo*, 5.1 ± 0.03 for *P. aeruginosa*) after 24 hours of incubation. However, the mixed culture potential with W9 and strains of (*L. innocua*, *L. ivanovii*, *Stap. aureus*, *E. coli*, *Sal. montevideo* and *P. aeruginosa*) were respectively regressive by percentages equal to (20.94%, 25.89%, 24.18%, 22.40%, 16.34% and 12.74%).

The lactic acid production rate was higher for the *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* strain (W9) ($77 \pm 1^\circ\text{D}$) after 24 hours of incubation, whereas for the other strains indicative of alterations and/or pathogens was ($57 \pm 1.25^\circ\text{D}$ for *L. innocua*, $60 \pm 2.82^\circ\text{D}$ for *L. ivanovii*, $59 \pm 1.54^\circ\text{D}$ for *Stap. aureus*, $57 \pm 1.89^\circ\text{D}$ for *E. coli*, $55 \pm 1^\circ\text{D}$ for *Sal. montevideo*, $54.5 \pm 2.59^\circ\text{D}$ for *P. aeruginosa*) in pure culture. These results are explained by the fact that the rate of acid production varies naturally with the bacterial metabolism, which can vary considerably from one species to another or from one strain to another [38].

In mixed culture with W9, an increase in lactic acid production was noted for the six indicator strains respectively (20.94%, 25.89%, 2.18%, 22.40%, 16.34% and 12.74%) after 24 hours. The growth rate of strains of alterations and/or pathogens in mixed culture with W9 appeared slower than their growth in pure culture, whose regression was: 22% for *L. innocua*, 23.41% for *L. ivanovii*, 18.57% for *Stap. aureus*, 16.17% for *E. coli*, 16.47% for *Sal. montevideo* and 15.48% for *P.s aeruginosa*.

Based on the pH monitoring (Fig. 6), the production of titratable acidity (Fig. 7) and enumeration of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* cells as well as strains of alterations and/or pathogens in the course of growth (Fig. 8), a great correlation between them was observed. This correlation represents an indirect index of bacterial development. In addition, the increase in growth rate was followed by a decrease in pH, which plays an increased role in the production of undissociated organic acids.

These results are good agreement with those reported by Acheson [39] who noted that the main reason for the antagonism provoked is the production of undissociated lactic acid which spreads easily through the bacterial cell wall, reducing the intracellular pH and slowing the activity metabolic rate of the bacterium.

Furthermore, Pieter *et al.* [40] reported that the rate of acid production is proportional to the bacterial mass. However, the decoupling of growth and metabolism can occur when growth slows or even stops, especially due to lactic acid. Thus, the enzymatic system of the bacteria can continue to convert lactose into lactic acid.

a)

b)

Fig. 6. Monitoring the pH

a) Pure cultures.

b) Mixed cultures.

Stap.: *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923)

LC.: *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090)

LV.: *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119)

E. coli: *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922)

Sal.: *Salmonella montevideo* (ATCC 3581).

Pa.: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853).

a)

b)

Fig. 7. The acidity kinetics (acidity °D)

a) Pure cultures

b) Mixed cultures

Stap. : *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923)

LC.: *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090)

LV.: *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119)

E. coli: *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922)

Sal.: *Salmonella Montevideo* (ATCC 3581).

Pa.: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853).

a)

b)

Fig. 8. The growth kinetics

a) Pure cultures

b) Mixed cultures

Stap. : *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923)

LC.: *Listeria innocua* (ATCC 33090)

LV.: *Listeria ivanovii* (ATCC 19119)

E. coli: *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922)

Sal.: *Salmonella montevideo* (ATCC 3581).

Pa.: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853).

CONCLUSION

Widespread in the natural environment, *Leuconostoc* have a major role in several fermentations due to their physiological characteristics. They are considered essential for maintaining the natural biological balance. Thus, this study aimed to investigate four samples of raw goat milk were collected in northwestern Algeria and used as sources of isolation of *Leuconostoc* spp.

12 isolates of *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* were obtained by sequential screening for catalase activity, oxidase and Gram stain plus morphological, chemical and MALDI-TOF tests. The in vitro results obtained showed that the strains of *Leuconostoc* spp, exhibited a broad spectrum of antagonistic activities against bacteria of alterations and / or pathogenic especially for the W9 strain which played a very important bio-preservative role linked to the production of compounds that inhibit the growth of pathogenic competitors and alterations by molecules due to their metabolism, such as hydrogen peroxide, organic acids like lactic acid (deadly for Gram-negative bacteria) plus production of inhibitory substances of protein nature "bacteriocin" (against gram-positive bacteria).

The results obtained showed that these isolates have an important antagonistic and conservative potential. For this purpose, it is necessary to carry out additional studies to accurately evaluate the mechanism of the antagonistic properties obtained from these antimicrobial substances for future use against infectious diseases caused by pathogenic bacteria and also as an alternative treatment instead of to use an antibiotic.

In addition, research should include a genomic study and proteomic characterization of isolated bacteriocins, to obtain a real image between the natural microbiology responsible for a high-quality product and to transfer this balanced potentiality for the production of modern, hygienic and standardized foods.

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